

SEARCHING POCKETS

Blo bzang ལྷོ་བཟང་། (Luozang 洛藏)*

Blo bzang lies in his unclean bed, looking at WeChat moments on his broken-screen phone. He sees Rab brtan's photos of traveling to Mtsho sngon po (Qinghai Lake) with his fiancé, driving a blue BMW, and eating in an opulent Western-style restaurant. They are enjoying steaks, spaghetti, and red-wine in two transparent long-stemmed goblets perched on a white cloth-covered table.

"Wow, cool," said Blo bzang.

He lies on his back, staring at the white ceiling.

He walked down a street, entered The China Profit Lottery Shop, bought a lottery, and won the lottery.

"I won the lottery and got one million RMB," he tells his father over the phone.

He flies First Class from Xi'an City to Zi ling (Xining). At the Zi ling Airport exit, family members and friends greet him with *kha btags*. Soon long, golden-colored silk scarves circle his neck.

He builds a Tibetan-style wooden house in his home village and purchases a Haihu District apartment in Zi ling City.

He shares his photos on Weibo, WeChat Moments, and videos on Kwai and Tik Tok with his girlfriend, G.yang sgron mtsho, a singer and movie actress famous in Tibetan areas. She has fascinated him for a long time. Now she is his. He prepares a gold necklace and an iPhone11 Pro Max for her as Valentine's gifts.

He lies on a luxurious sofa in the living room, waiting for her to arrive when "Bang! Bang! Bang!" sounds at the door.

He jumps up and rushes to open the door.

"It's time to pay your rent. It's 300 RMB this month," the landlord says.

He searches all of his pockets twice, finds nothing, and promises, "I'll pay you tomorrow."

TIBETAN TERMS

blo bzang ལྷོ་བཟང་།

g.yang sgron mtsho གཡང་སྒྲོན་མཚོ།

kha btags ཁ་བཏགས།

mtsho sngon po མཚོ་སྒྲོན་པོ།

rab brtan རབ་བརྟན།

zi ling ཟི་ལིང་།

CHINESE TERMS

Haihu 海湖

Kwai, Kuaishou 快手

Qinghai 青海

Xi'an 西安

Xining 西宁

WeChat, Weibo 微信

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